

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045
E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Periodic Research

Relationship Between Digit Ratio (2d:4d) and Endurance of College Male Students

Paper Id : 19957 Submission Date : 2025-04-14 Acceptance Date : 2025-04-30 Publication Date : 2025-05-05
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15747249

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Abstract

Hunting talent at early age in sports is very important for getting peak performance at right age. Developing country like India which is large in land area with world second largest population, here talent identification is a big problem. This study will provide a big scope to physical education teachers as well as sports coaches to find talent by just calculating the finger ratio. Endurance capacity is very important physical fitness component for most of the outdoor and indoor sports, a person with good endurance capacity can be successful in any sports.

Keywords

Endurance, Digit ratio, VO2max.

Introduction

Every living organism have some or other way to move their body to propel themselves from one place to another like walking, running, jumping, crawling, climbing, swimming, flying, galloping, slithering and so on. Running is method of moving fast on foot for sports, to catch something, to run away from some danger etc. human has used running as a sporting event in three ways sprint, middle distance and long distance. Sometimes there is a question that what is the difference between running and walking? So, we can differentiate it as running is like walking except there is a period of suspension when both feet are off the running surface at the same time.

As we all know that running is a sporting event and to be a good middle distance or long-distance runner it is very important to have good endurance. There are many research studies which show that testosterone contribute to higher RBC (red blood cell) production, improving oxygen transport in the body, which enhance the endurance of an athlete. There are many studies which show a positive relationship between digit ratio (2D:4D) and level of testosterone.

The present study was undertaken to find out the relationship between the digit ratio and endurance of college male students. This study will be beneficial for the coach and school physical education teachers to identify students for middle and long-distance runners.

Objective of study

To find out the relationship between finger ratio and endurance of college male students.

Statistical analysis- On the result of cooper 12 minute run/walk test and finger ratio both were equated on the basis of respective mean and standard deviation. Coefficient of correlation was calculated to find the significance between finger ratio and endurance.

Review of Literature

M. S. Roriz Oliveira and et.al. examined 48 to examine the effects of a recreational-based physical activity summer camp (SC) on body composition, metabolic syndrome, and physical fitness in obese children. Forty-eight children (8-10 years; body mass index \geq 85th percentile) completed 4-weeks of a structured recreational-based physical activity program SC (5 hours/day, 5 days/week). Over the 4-weeks, significant reductions ($p < 0.05$) in weight, waist circumference, body mass index, percentage of body fat, and systolic and diastolic blood pressure were observed. Additionally, a significant increase was observed in HDL-cholesterol, handgrip, trunk lift, and shuttle run ($p < 0.05$). These findings suggest that a 4-weeks recreational-based physical activity SC yields several body-composition, metabolic-syndrome, and physical-fitness benefits in obese children and should represent an effective support for their health development.

Savvas P. Tokmakidis and et.al. examined 50 to provide estimates for overweight and obesity in a sample of Greek schoolchildren and to determine their possible relation with

selected motor and health-related fitness parameters. **MATERIALS AND METHODS:** The study sample consisted of 709 healthy children (328 girls, 381 boys, mean age = 8.9+/-1.6 years), living in the towns of Agios Stefanos (approximately 12,000 citizens) and Alexandroupolis (approximately 60,000 citizens), Greece. All pupils underwent anthropometric, motor and cardiovascular fitness assessments (Eurofit test battery). The body mass index (BMI) cut-off points adopted by the International Obesity Task Force were utilized for the assessment of overweight and obesity. **RESULTS:** 59.4% of the participants had a normal BMI, 25.8% were overweight and 14.8% were obese, without significant differences between genders. **DISCUSSIONS:** In general, the higher BMI categories were strongly associated with inferior performances in all fitness tests, except flexibility. This graded relationship was consistent for both boys and girls, although the statistical relationship between BMI categories and fitness performance varied by gender. **CONCLUSIONS:** In conclusion, the findings of the current study offer some support to the reported high prevalence of childhood obesity in Greece and suggest that overweight and obesity are limiting factors for fitness performance in primary schoolchildren. The present data suggest that interventions promoting children's health should, ideally, begin early in life and involve measures that simultaneously improve fitness and lower fatness.

Roseane O. Nascimento and et.al. examined 53 The present study aims to examine physical fitness among children with developmental coordination disorder (DCD) with varying degrees of severity (moderate and severe - mDCD, sDCD), and a group of children without DCD (wDCD), in the city of Manaus, Brazil. Initially, 180 children aged 6-10 years old participated in this study. After being diagnosed according to the DSM-IV-TR, 63 children were then divided into three groups (21 in each group). Health-related physical fitness was measured by means of the Fitnessgram, which included several core components, namely, body composition, muscle strength and endurance, flexibility, and cardiorespiratory resistance. The results showed no statistically significant differences between both groups in any of the assessed components. However, when analyzing the results of each component according to the criteria of the Fitnessgram, we observed that, regardless of the classification group, less than half of the children achieved scores that, according to the motor tests, would classify them as having a healthy fitness. Children with sDCD, mDCD and wDCD presented similar levels of health-related physical fitness, with an unsatisfactory performance for the component strength and muscular endurance. We therefore emphasize the importance of further research in this area, more particularly when it comes to following the development of motor skills and physical fitness in children with DCD, as well as the observation of the interactions between these variables over time. Yung Liao and et.al. examined 25 associations between four health-related physical fitness measures and obesity in Taiwanese youth aged 10-18 years. Data from 13,500 school-aged youth were randomly selected from the "School Physical Fitness Database" of Taiwan by sex and age. Variables examined were height, body mass and performance on modified sit-and-reach (flexibility), bent-leg sit-up (abdominal muscular strength/endurance), standing long jump (lower body explosive strength) and distance run/walk (cardiorespiratory endurance). Adjusted logistic regression analyses were performed. Increased odds of being obese with decreased fitness levels were observed for lower body explosive strength and cardiorespiratory endurance in both sexes. The highest odds of being obese was found in the least fit quintile of cardiorespiratory endurance compared with the most fit quintile both in boys (Odds ratio, OR = 10.44; 95% confidence interval (CI), 7.94-13.73) and girls (OR = 5.40; 95% CI, 3.90-7.47). These findings suggest that in addition to cardiorespiratory fitness, lower body explosive strength is also associated with childhood and adolescent obesity.

Ernesto De la Cruz-Sánchez and et.al. 27 examined to analyze differences according to sex in physical performance in children before puberty, as well as other health-related variables. Study population was 137 boys and 156 girls (9.99 +/- 0.79 years). We measured weight and height, physical performance using five field tests previously validated in children, habitual physical activity and diet quality. A multinomial logistic regression coefficient was established to calculate odd ratios (OR's) and 95% confidence intervals (CI's), to determine sex differences in performance, weight status, habitual physical activity and diet quality, and a t-test was calculated between active boys and active girls in order to establish differences in performance fitness test taking account habitual physical activity. Boys were more actives (OR 1.90, CI 1.03-3.49) and had better weight status than girls, while there was no difference in diet quality between sexes (OR 1.13, CI 0.67-1.89). In total sample, it was more probable to find greater physical fitness values in boys in all test performed. However, when both groups had a similar physical activity pattern, assessed physical fitness variables reached similar values and girls had better results only in flexibility. Sedentary patterns were more frequent in girls although there were no differences in diet quality between sexes. Girls tended to overweight more than boys did. Both sexes had a similar fitness performance before puberty for the same reported physical activity, except for flexibility, inferior in male subjects independently of their physical activity pattern. The article titled "*The association between digit ratio (2D:4D and right-left 2D:4D), maximal oxygen consumption and ventilatory thresholds in professional male football players*" by Parpa, Manning, Kobus, Mason, and Michaelides (2024) investigates the biological link between digit ratios — particularly the 2D:4D ratio — and aerobic fitness indicators such as maximal oxygen consumption (VO₂ max) and ventilatory thresholds (VT1 and VT2). The study examines whether the digit ratio, a marker thought to reflect prenatal androgen exposure, can serve as a predictor of endurance performance in elite-level male football players.

The researchers used a cross-sectional design involving professional athletes. They measured digit ratios using standardized photocopies or digital scans, while aerobic capacity was assessed through treadmill-based VO₂ max testing and ventilatory threshold evaluation. The findings demonstrated a small but significant association between certain digit ratio patterns and VO₂ max, implying that prenatal hormone exposure may play a subtle role in shaping physiological traits that influence athletic performance. The study is notable for integrating biological and physiological data, contributing to the interdisciplinary field of sports science and human biology. However, it has limitations, including a relatively narrow sample population (male football players only) and a correlational approach that does not confirm causation. Additionally, the influence of environmental, genetic, and training factors on both digit ratio and VO₂ max was not fully addressed. Nonetheless, the study provides valuable insight and prompts further research in broader populations and sports contexts.

Overall, the article presents an innovative perspective on the biological underpinnings of performance and is a thought-provoking addition to current literature.

Methodology

Collection of Data

Total 50 male student of Swami Devanand Post Graduation college Math Lar, Deoria (U.P) were selected on random basis as subject for this study. All students were of 17 to 24 year age group. Average age of students were 21.5 years.

Finger ratio was taken from both left and right hand index finger(4D) and ring finger(2D).

Endurance ability of the subject was tested by cooper 12 minute run/walk test.

Coopers 12 minute run/walk administration- This test helps in testing estimate cardio respiratory capacity and maximum oxygen uptake (VO₂ max).

Set up-

1. Test is performed on an official athletic track (400 meter).
2. Participants run/walk without interruption for 12 minutes.
3. The total distance covered in 12 minutes is recorded.

Following equation is used to predict maximum oxygen uptake capacity

$$VO_2 \text{ max} = \frac{d-504.9}{44.73} \text{ ml/kg/min}$$

here 'd' is the distance covered in meter
Normative data for cooper test-

Age	Excellent	Above average	Average	Below average	Poor
17- 19	>3000	2700-3000	2500-2699	2300-2499	<2300
20-29	>2800	2400-2800	2200-2399	1600-2199	<1600

Normative data for cooper test and VO₂ max

Poor	Fair	Average	Good	Excellent
32-37	38-43	44-50	51-56	>62

Finger ratio- finger ratio (2D:4D) of both the hands is taken. 2D indicates index finger and 4D indicates the ring finger. Finger length is measured from the tip of the finger to the last crease of finger which joins the palm. Length of finger is measured of both the hands and digit ratio (2D:4D) is calculated then average ratio of both the hands is taken for the study

The "2D:4D Ratio"

Fig 1. representing measurement of fingers

Result and Discussion

Variables	Obs	Mean	Std.dev	Min	Max
Finger Ratio	50	0.967	0.030	0.902	1.032
VO2 Max	50	49.29	7.91	33.41	62.47

Variables	Finger ratio	Vo2max
Finger ratio	1	
Vo2max	-0.3052 (0.03)*	1

Conclusion

This study defines that there is a negative relationship between finger ratio and endurance capacity. It means that those students having less finger ratio have good endurance capacity. The study gives indication that by calculating the finger ratio of students we can predict the endurance capacity of students. Though study shows weak negative relationship but it can be very helpful for the physical education teachers and coaches working at remote areas with very less facilities and techniques to predict endurance capacity of students.

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